

Ultraviolet Spectra of 1,2-Dicyano Esters and Related Compounds. An Anomalous UV Absorption Band

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UV spectra of several new 1,2-dicyano esters (3a, 3f and 3g) and 1,1,2-tricyano compounds (3n, 3p and 3q) exhibit an anomalous absorption maxima around 240 nm in alcoholic solution. On the basis of the spectra of different types of related compounds studied (3h to 3m, and 3o), it is concluded that the keto \rightleftharpoons enol tautomerism, suggested earlier, is not responsible for the observed UV maxima. The present study, further, indicated the involvement of the cyano group in the mechanism of absorption. IR spectra of the cyano compounds (3a, 3c and 3p) exhibit bands at 1935 and 2050 cm^{-1} in CHCl_3 -EtOH^(1:2) and CHCl_3 -MeOH^(1:2) solutions respectively. The same bands are also observed in the IR spectra of acetonitrile, ethyl cyanoacetate, malononitrile and ethyl 2,3-dicyano-2,3-dimethylbutyrate in the same solvent mixtures. These bands are tentatively assigned to the hydrogen bonding between the proton donor alcohols and the π -electrons of the cyano group.

BANERJEE and Kasturi¹ in 1957 observed that several saturated 1,2-dicyano esters of the type **1** show an absorption band around 245 nm

Fig. 1.

band. On the basis of these observations, it was suggested that the anomalous absorption maximum in these compounds was due to the keto-enol tautomerism $1 \rightleftharpoons 2$ with an unusual solvent dependence.

Fig. 2.

in alcoholic solution in their UV spectra. Later Kasturi et al.² observed that this band was invariably present in the UV spectra of all such 1,2-dicyano esters, they examined, but not in non-polar solvents like heptane or polar solvents like acetonitrile. Further, they showed that the extinction coefficient increased with dilution and that the presence of the active hydrogen on the carbon carrying the cyano and the alkoxy carbonyl groups and the β -cyano group were essential for the occurrence of the above

However, the solvent behaviour of the absorption maximum, i.e. the absence of the absorption band in non-polar and non-hydroxylic solvents and the increase in the intensity with dilution, was exactly the reverse of that observed in the case of open-chain β -diketones/ β -keto esters, which exist as the chelate structure in non-polar solvents like heptane. In alcoholic solutions of β -diketones/ β -keto esters, however, there is less of chelation because of the competition with their comparatively weak intermolecular hydrogen bonding with the solvent molecules, resulting in maxima with low extinction co-efficients, as compared with those observed in

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$J=7\text{Hz}$), 4.37 (q , 4H, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$, $J=7\text{Hz}$), 4.22(S , 1H, CH) and 4.28 δ (S , 1H, CH). The two equal intensity signals at 4.22 and 4.28 δ from apparently equivalent hydrogens may be due to the existence of a mixture of diastereomers in the product.

Addition of hydrogen cyanide to isopropylidene-malononitrile gave a mixture of two compounds, which could be separated by fractional crystallisation from methanol. One of them was the expected tricyano compound (**3n**) and the other one was shown to be the dimer (**4**), by comparison of its IR, UV spectra and mixed m.p. determination with an authentic sample¹³.

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Fig. 4.

In view of the low yield of the required tricyano compound (**3n**) by the above method, it was prepared later by condensation of acetonecyanohydrin with the sodium salt of malononitrile in 70% yield.

Diethyl 1-cyano-2, 2-dimethylsuccinate¹⁴ (**3i**) was hydrolysed to ethane-1, 1, 2-tricarboxylic acid, which on esterification gave the triester (**3l**)¹⁵.

All attempts to prepare ethyl 1, 2-dicyano-2-methoxybutyrate (**3b**) and 1-cyano-2-ethoxycarbonyl-2-methoxybutyronitrile (**3e**) by different methods were unsuccessful.

SPECTRAL PROPERTIES

UV spectra with λ_{max} and ϵ_{max} at different concentrations in alcohol of 1, 2-dicyano esters, 1, 1, 2-tricyano and related compounds are given in table 1.

TABLE I

Compound	Max (nm)	EtOH—NaOH			
		—	Conc. gm moles/litre	max	—
3a	247	850	6.1×10^{-4}	—	—
		2100	5.45×10^{-5}	—	—
3c	245	500	3.6×10^{-4}	—	—
		1050	1.39×10^{-4}	—	—
		1200	1.07×10^{-4}	245	7940
		1850	5.45×10^{-5}	—	—
3d	246	160	2.06×10^{-3}	—	—
		260	5.14×10^{-4}	—	—
3f	244	3080	1.07×10^{-4}	—	—
		6000	5.45×10^{-5}	—	—
3g	245	9550	5.45×10^{-5}	—	—
3h—3m	—	—	—	—	—
3n	231	950	5.45×10^{-4}	—	—
		1570	2.7×10^{-4}	—	—
		6300	5.45×10^{-5}	—	—
		5820	9.00×10^{-5}	231	15,140
3o	—	—	—	—	—
3p	231	550	9.0×10^{-4}	—	—
		750	5.45×10^{-4}	—	—
		3450	5.45×10^{-5}	—	—
		1600	2.7×10^{-4}	—	—
3q	224	11,500	5.45×10^{-5}	—	—
		1600	2.7×10^{-4}	—	—

Discussions

It may be observed that diethylmalonate, ethyl cyanoacetate and malononitrile do not show any absorption in their UV spectra. 1, 2-Dicyano esters (3a, 3f and 3g), however, show the anomalous absorption band around 245 nm in alcoholic solutions. Replacement of either the β -cyano group by an ethoxycarbonyl group (3i) or the α -hydrogen atom by $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CN}$ (3h) in the aforementioned compounds leads to the disappearance of the abnormal absorption band, thus confirming the earlier observations of Kasturi et al.²

Fig. 5.

Cyano diesters (3j and 3k) in which the α -cyano group has been replaced by an ethoxycarbonyl group, and the triester (3l), in which both the α - and the β -cyano groups are replaced by ethoxycarbonyl groups, do not show the absorption in their UV spectra, indicating the involvement of the cyano group in the tautomerisation. Further increase in the number of alcoxycarbonyl groups, e.g. the tetraester (3m), also does not show the effect. In contrast, the tricyano compounds (3n and 3p) in which the single ester group of the 1, 2-dicyano ester system is replaced by the more electronegative cyano group, absorb more strongly than the corresponding dicyano esters (3c and 3d)² and exhibit the same solvent behaviour but with a hypsochromic shift. The effect of the comparatively stronger electron withdrawing β -cyano group received support from the observation that the introduction of a second electron withdrawing group on the β -carbon atom, as in the compounds (3f and 3g) enhanced the intensity of the absorption, while introduction of electron donating groups at the β -carbon atom, as in the compound (3c), comparatively reduced the intensity.

These data clearly show that enolisation involving alcoxycarbonyl group, as suggested earlier²,

* Almange¹⁶ has provided IR evidence against keteniminisation. However, his conclusions are based only on the study of IR spectra in solvents like dioxane, carbon tetrachloride and acetonitrile in which the anomalous UV absorption band is not observed.

is not responsible for the anomalous UV absorption of 1, 2-dicyano esters.

It has been observed by us, as well as by Almange¹⁶, that the addition of a base to the ethanolic solutions of 1, 2-dicyano and 1, 1, 2-tricyano compounds leads to considerable increase in the intensity of the absorption maxima. This is obviously due to the enimisation of the cyano group in these compounds giving rise to the mesomeric anion (5), as a consequence of solvation with ethanol, in which the ketenimine anion character should predominate.

In order to provide an evidence in favour or against* keteniminisation, the study of the IR spectra of the compounds (3a to 3q) in chloroform and chloroform ethanol/methanol mixtures was taken, and it was observed that while the compounds (3a, 3c and 3p) absorbed at 1935 cm^{-1} in chloroform-ethanol (1:2) mixture and at 2050 cm^{-1} in chloroform-methanol (1:2) mixture, these bands were absent in pure chloroform solutions. Initially¹⁷, we assigned these bands to the ketenimine structure. But, later, it was found that compounds like acetonitrile, ethyl cyanoacetate, malononitrile and ethyl 2, 3-dicyano-2, 3-dimethylbutyrate¹⁸ also show the same peaks. In view of these results, the IR evidence is not conclusive. The above bands probably result from the hydrogen bonding between the proton donor alcohols and the π electrons of the $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ bond^{19,17b}.

Experimental

All melting points and boiling points reported are uncorrected. The UV spectra were taken in 95% ethanol (unless otherwise stated) on Beckmann DU and Unicam SP-700A spectrophotometers. The IR spectra were recorded with Perkin Elmer model 137B and UR10 Carl Zeiss spectrophotometers and NMR spectra were taken on a Varian A-60 instrument using TMS as internal standard.

General Procedure for the Addition of Hydrogen Cyanide to α , β -Unsaturated Compounds :

An ethanolic solution of the α , β -unsaturated compound was added to a cooled (0°) and stirred

solution of potassium cyanide in water, stirred at 0° for about 20 minutes (unless otherwise specified) and then acidified by slow addition of 20% HCl in two lots (at an interval of 20 minutes). The mixture was then diluted with water, extracted with ether and the ether extracts washed with ice-cold brine, water and dried Na₂SO₄. The solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the residue purified by crystallisation or fractionation.

Ethyl 1, 2-dicyanocaproate (3a) :

Addition of a solution of potassium cyanide (17.1 g.) in water (43 ml.) to a cooled and stirred solution of ethyl n-butyridenecyanoacetate²⁰ (22 g.) in ethanol (100 ml.) gave the dicyano ester (3a, 15 g.) b.p. 143-47°/2 mm., n_D^{28} 1.4435, IR ν_{\max}^{neat} : 2273 and 1748 cm⁻¹. (Found : C, 61.49 ; H, 7.3 ; N, 14.36. C₁₀H₁₄N₂O₂ requires : C, 61.83 ; H, 7.27 ; N, 14.42%).

Diethyl 1-cyano-2-methylmaleate

A mixture of ethyl pyruvate (4g.), ethyl cyanoacetate (3 g.), ammonium acetate (0.4 g.), acetic acid (1 ml.) and benzene (30 ml.) was refluxed with continuous water separation till no more of water separated. The mixture was cooled, washed with water and dried. Removal of the solvent followed by fractionation of the residue gave diethyl 1-cyano-2-methylmaleate (2.9 g.), b.p. 130°/2 mm., n_D^{28} 1.4581. UV $\epsilon_{\text{EtOH}}^{\text{max}}$: 224 mm (ϵ 7500), IR ν_{\max}^{neat} : 2247, 1739 and 1621 cm⁻¹ (Found : C, 56.63 ; H, 5.98 ; N, 7.01. C₁₀H₁₃NO₄ requires : C, 56.86 ; H, 6.20 ; N, 6.63%).

Diethyl 1, 2-dicyano-2-methylsuccinate (3f)

Hydrogen cyanide addition to a solution of the aforementioned diethyl 1-cyano-2-methylmaleate (1.6 g.) in ethanol (10 ml.) using potassium cyanide (1 g.) in water (2.5 ml.) gave the dicyano ester (3f, 1.35 g.), b.p. 95-98°/3.8 × 10⁻³ mm., n_D^{28} 1.4450, IR ν_{\max}^{neat} : 2273 and 1751 cm⁻¹, NMR (CDCl₃) : 1.35 (t, 6H, COOCH₂CH₃, J=7Hz), 1.91 (s, 3H, CH₃), 4.35 (q, 4H, COOCH₂CH₃, J=7Hz) and 4.25δ (s, 1H, CH) (Found : C, 55.55 ; H, 6.04 ; N, 11.49. C₁₁H₁₄N₂O₄ requires : C, 55.45 ; H, 5.92 ; N, 11.76%).

Ethyl 1, 2-dicyano-1-cyanoethylcaproate (3h) :

Cyanoethylation of ethyl 1, 2-dicyanocaproate (3a, 10 g.) in dioxane (15 ml.) using acrylonitrile (2.75 g.) and triton B (0.8 ml) gave after fractionation the cyanoethylcaproate (3h, 9 g.), b.p. 125°/2.308 × 10⁻³

mm, n_D^{28} 1.4592, IR ν_{\max}^{neat} : 2262 and 1748 cm⁻¹ (Found : C, 62.91 ; H, 6.90 ; N, 16.73. C₁₃H₁₇N₃O₂ requires : C, 63.14 ; H, 6.93 ; N, 16.99%).

Ethyl 1-ethoxycarbonyl -2-cyano-2-methylbutyrate (3j)

A mixture of solutions of isopropylidenemalonate²¹ (15 g.) in ethanol (60 ml.) and potassium cyanide (10.1 g.) in water (20 ml.) was allowed to stand for two days. Addition of hydrochloric acid followed by the usual work-up gave a gum which was chromatographed on neutral alumina (200 g.). Elution with hexane-benzene (1:1) afforded the cyano diester (3j, 4.5 g.), b.p. 130-4°/c mm, n_D^{28} 1.4385, IR ν_{\max}^{neat} : 2270 and 1745 cm⁻¹ (Found : C, 58.42 ; H, 7.52 ; N, 6.30. C₁₁H₁₇NO₄ requires : C, 58.13 ; H, 7.54 ; N, 6.16%).

Ethyl 1-ethoxycarbonyl-2-cyanoacproate (3k)

Hydrogen cyanide addition to diethyl n-butyridenemalonate²² (10 g.) in ethanol (100 ml.) using potassium cyanide (6.1 g.) and water (15 ml.) gave the dicyano ester (3k, 5.5 g.), b.p. 127-32°/2.5 mm, n_D^{28} 1.4216, IR ν_{\max}^{neat} : 2270 and 1748 cm⁻¹ (Found : C, 59.62 ; H, 7.81 ; N, 5.73. C₁₂H₁₉NO₄ requires : C, 59.73 ; H, 7.94 ; N, 5.81%).

1-Cyano-2, 2-dimethylsuccinodinitrile (3n)

(a) Hydrogen cyanide addition to a solution of isopropylidenemalononitrile¹³ (12 g.) in ethanol (60 ml.) using potassium cyanide (14.7 g.) in water (35 ml) gave after usual work-up a crystalline solid (13.5 g.). TLC (in CHCl₃) of this solid indicated it to be a mixture of two compounds. This was separated by repeated fractional crystallisation from methanol. One of the fractions (1.5 g.), m.p. 72-73°, R_F value 0.3, was the tricyano compound (3n). IR $\nu_{\max}^{\text{nujol}}$: 2262 cm⁻¹, NMR (CDCl₃) : 1.63 (s, 6H) and 4.1 δ (s, 1H) (Found : C, 63.40 ; H, 5.22 ; N, 31.56. C₇H₇N₃ requires : C, 63.14 ; H, 5.30 ; N, 31.56%).

The second fraction (9.6 g.), m.p. 172-73°, R_F value 0.15, was identical with the known dimer¹³ (4) of isopropylidenemalononitrile (Reported¹³ m.p. 170-75°)

(b) A suspension of the sodium salt of malononitrile prepared from malononitrile (10 g.), sodium (3.15 g.) and dry ethanol (50 ml.) was added to a cooled (0°) and stirred solution of acetonecyanohydrin (13 g.) in ethanol (50 ml) over a period of 45

minutes. The stirring was continued for two hours at the same temperature and the mixture was left overnight (room temp.). It was cooled, diluted with water (300 ml) and acidified with 2 N HCl when the tricyano compound (3n, 14.1 g.) was obtained. It was recrystallised from methanol, m.p. 75-76°.

1-Cyano-1-cyanoethyl-2, 2-dimethylsuccinodinitrile (3o)

Cyanoethylation of (3n, 1 g.) using acrylonitrile (0.4 g.), triton B (0.1 ml.) and dioxan (10 ml.) gave the tertacyano compound (3o, 1.2 g.) which was crystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 105-6°, IR $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{nujol}}$: 2273 cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 64.49 ; H, 5.38 ; N, 30.03. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4$ requires : C, 64.50 ; H, 5.41 ; N, 30.09%).

1-Cyanocyclohexylcyanoacetonitrile (3p)

Hydrogen cyanide addition to cyclohexylidene-malononitrile (10 g.) in ethanol (100 ml) was carried out as before using potassium cyanide (9.1 g.) and water (20 ml.). The crystalline tricyano compound (3p, 9.8 g.), obtained on filtering the mixture, was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 117-8°, IR $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{nujol}}$: 2270 cm^{-1} , NMR (CDCl_3) ; 1.7 (s, 10H) and 4.13 δ (s, 1H) (Found : C, 69.18 ; H, 6.58 ; N, 23.95. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3$ requires : C, 69.34 ; H, 6.40 ; N, 24.26%).

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